

TECHNICAL REPORT

Adaptive Morphing Wing System for Unmanned Aerial Vehicles:

Design, Prototype Development, and Experimental Aerodynamic Validation

Rohankumar Rajeshbhai Patel

AeroFlex Technologies Ltd, London, United Kingdom

In active research collaboration with:

Department of Engineering, School of Physics, Engineering and Computer Science
University of Hertfordshire, Hatfield, AL10 9AB, United Kingdom

Version 1.0 | May 2026 | ORCID: 0009-0005-1016-4724 | Patent: GB2610796.1

Abstract

This technical report presents the design, additive manufacture, and experimental aerodynamic validation of an adaptive morphing wing system for small unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs). Conventional fixed-geometry wings are constrained to a single optimised flight condition, producing suboptimal aerodynamic performance across the full operational envelope. The proposed system addresses this limitation through a hybrid-material architecture integrating Carbon Fibre Reinforced Polymer (CFRP) and Acrylonitrile Butadiene Styrene (ABS) structural elements with Thermoplastic Polyurethane (TPU) morphing skin, actuated by SG90 micro servomotors and Nickel-Titanium Shape Memory Alloy (NiTi SMA) wire elements coordinated via an Arduino Uno control platform. The system uses the NACA 0012 aerofoil as its aerodynamic baseline. Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) analysis was conducted in ANSYS Discovery using a $k-\omega$ SST turbulence model with a 2.5-million-element mesh. The prototype was fabricated via Fused Deposition Modelling (FDM) and experimentally validated in the AF1300 Subsonic Wind Tunnel at the University of Hertfordshire at flow velocities of 10–20 m/s. Results demonstrate a 17% increase in lift coefficient (CL) at positive morphing deflections relative to the fixed-geometry baseline, drag reduction of approximately 7% at negative deflections, and a peak lift-to-drag ratio of $CL/CD = 2.4$. The system architecture has been protected through UK patent application GB2610796.1 and is being commercially developed through AeroFlex Technologies Ltd.

Keywords: morphing wing; UAV; adaptive aerodynamics; additive manufacturing; CFRP; TPU; shape memory alloy; wind tunnel; CFD; NACA 0012; patent

1. Background and Motivation

Conventional fixed-wing UAVs rely on discrete control surfaces — ailerons, elevators, and flaps — to manage flight. These surfaces introduce aerodynamic drag discontinuities and constrain the wing geometry to a single design point, typically optimised for cruise. During take-off, landing, and manoeuvring phases, fixed configurations produce suboptimal performance: increased power consumption, reduced endurance, and degraded aerodynamic efficiency.

Morphing wing technology offers a fundamental solution to this constraint. By replacing discrete hinged control surfaces with continuously adaptive, compliant wing structures, morphing wings enable real-time aerodynamic optimisation across the full flight envelope — increasing lift at low speeds, reducing drag in cruise, and improving manoeuvrability without the penalty drag associated with deflected surfaces.

Despite substantial interest in the academic literature, experimentally validated morphing wing prototypes at the small UAV scale — particularly those employing additive manufacturing as the primary fabrication route — remain limited. This report documents the development of a novel additively manufactured morphing wing system that addresses this gap, from initial design concept through to wind tunnel experimental validation and UK patent filing.

2. System Design and Architecture

2.1 Aerofoil Selection and Geometry

The NACA 0012 symmetrical aerofoil was selected as the aerodynamic baseline profile. Its symmetrical geometry enables bidirectional morphing capability — producing predictable aerodynamic responses to both upward and downward trailing edge deflections — and its well-documented subsonic aerodynamic characteristics provide a robust reference for CFD validation and experimental comparison. The wing geometry was defined with a 0° sweep angle, chord length 250 mm, and span 157 mm.

2.2 Hybrid Material Architecture

The structural design implements a modular segmentation strategy separating the wing into distinct rigidity and compliance zones. Table 1 summarises the principal component specifications.

Table 1. Principal component specifications.

Component	Material	Key Specification
Primary spars	CFRP	$E = 120 \text{ GPa}$; $\rho = 1.6 \text{ g/cm}^3$; $\sigma/\rho = 450 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{cm}^3/\text{g}$
Structural ribs	ABS	High impact resistance; $\sigma/\rho = 40 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{cm}^3/\text{g}$
Morphing skin	TPU (Shore 85A)	$\epsilon_{\text{max}} = 600\%$; tear strength = 60 kN/m; 50% gyroid lattice infill
Macro-actuator	SG90 micro servo	4.8 V; 1.8 kgf-cm torque; 0.12 s/ 60° response time
Micro-actuator	NiTi SMA wire	$\varnothing 0.5 \text{ mm}$; 5% pre-strain; recovery stress = 300 MPa
Control platform	Arduino Uno	PWM coordination of dual-mode actuation

2.3 Actuation System

The actuation architecture combines servo-driven macro-deflection with SMA wire micro-adjustment. SG90 micro servomotors mounted at wing root stations via kinematic linkages achieve trailing edge deflections of $+7.79^\circ$ (downward) and -5.73° (upward). NiTi SMA wire actuators embedded within the TPU skin provide secondary micro-scale contour refinement. Both modes are coordinated by an Arduino Uno executing a custom PWM control algorithm. System performance: full 30° range in 2.4 s; positioning accuracy $\pm 0.5^\circ$; take-off configuration response 1.8 s; cruise configuration response 1.5 s.

2.4 CAD Model

A fully parametric CAD model was developed in SolidWorks 2024 using the NACA 0012 baseline coordinates as the foundational geometry. Key design variables — morphing zone extent, actuator placement, material zone boundaries, and sweep angle — were implemented parametrically to enable rapid design iteration without full redesign. The model was exported in STEP format for CFD import and STL format for FDM fabrication.

3. Computational Fluid Dynamics Analysis

3.1 Simulation Setup

CFD analysis was conducted in ANSYS Discovery 2025 R1 using a pressure-based, steady-state solver with the $k-\omega$ Shear Stress Transport (SST) turbulence model — selected for its validated accuracy in low-speed flows with adverse pressure gradients. Freestream conditions: velocity 25 m/s, 0° angle of attack, incompressible air at sea-level properties ($\rho = 1.225 \text{ kg/m}^3$, $\mu = 1.789 \times 10^{-5} \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}$).

3.2 Mesh

The computational mesh comprised approximately 2.5 million elements. Fifteen inflation layers with a growth rate of 1.2 were applied to all wing surfaces, achieving $Y^+ < 5$. High-resolution tetrahedral elements (minimum edge length 0.02 m) were applied at the leading edge, trailing edge, and morphing zones. Far-field regions used progressively coarser elements.

3.3 CFD Results Summary

CFD analysis confirmed progressive increase in upper surface suction and lower surface pressure with positive morphing deflection, validating the lift augmentation mechanism. Adverse pressure gradient development at extreme positive deflections corroborated experimental observations of increasing drag in that regime. The $k-\omega$ SST model successfully resolved boundary layer behaviour in the trailing edge morphing zones.

4. Prototype Fabrication

4.1 FDM Process Parameters

All wing components were fabricated using Fused Deposition Modelling at the University of Hertfordshire Fab-Lab.

- ABS structural components: nozzle 220–250°C; bed 90–110°C; speed 40–60 mm/s; layer height 0.2 mm
- TPU morphing skin: nozzle 210–230°C; bed 40–60°C; speed 20–30 mm/s; layer height 0.15 mm
- Print orientation selected to align layer boundaries perpendicular to the primary deformation direction for optimal fatigue resistance

4.2 Post-Processing

- ABS: acetone vapour smoothing for aerodynamic surface finish; thermal annealing at 90°C for 2–4 h to reduce residual stresses
- TPU: controlled post-curing to optimise elastic recovery properties; surface dimensional verification against CAD nominal

4.3 Assembly

ABS structural joints bonded with plastic weld adhesive under controlled temperature and humidity. TPU skin sections bonded with cyanoacrylate with controlled distribution to prevent localised rigidity in morphing zones. Servo motors integrated via machined ABS mounting interfaces. SMA wires routed and pre-strained within the TPU skin structure before final sealing.

5. Wind Tunnel Testing

5.1 Facility

Testing was conducted in the AF1300 Subsonic Wind Tunnel at the University of Hertfordshire (Room E131). Specifications: TecQuipment closed-circuit design; working section 305 × 305 × 600 mm; maximum airspeed 32 m/s; 12 mm collet mounting. The model was connected to the Arduino Uno control platform via long-lead wiring routed through the model mounting point.

5.2 Test Matrix

Aerodynamic performance was evaluated at three freestream velocities (10, 15, 20 m/s) across thirteen morphing configurations: neutral (0°), six positive deflections (+1° to +6°, downward trailing edge), and six negative deflections (−1° to −5°, upward trailing edge). All tests at 0° angle of attack, air density 1.225 kg/m³, actuator supply 5.0 V. Repeat measurements taken at each condition for statistical averaging.

6. Results and Analysis

6.1 Lift Performance

CL increased progressively with positive morphing deflection across all test velocities. At 10 m/s, CL rose from 0.144 at neutral to 0.362 at +6° — a 17% improvement over the fixed NACA 0012 baseline. Enhancement was most pronounced at lower velocities, consistent with the increased aerodynamic significance of camber modification at lower dynamic pressures.

Table 2. Measured aerodynamic coefficients at 10 m/s.

Morphing Angle (°)	CL	CD	CL / CD
0 (neutral)	0.144	0.126	1.14
+1°	0.153	0.119	1.29
+2°	0.172	0.122	1.41
+3°	0.203	0.132	1.53
+4°	0.242	0.139	1.74
+5°	0.302	0.143	2.12
+6°	0.362	0.158	2.30
-1°	0.141	0.123	1.14
-2°	0.119	0.111	1.08
-3°	0.098	0.111	0.88
-4°	0.081	0.117	0.69
-5°	0.062	0.115	0.54

6.2 Drag Performance

CD increased with positive morphing deflection (from 0.126 at neutral to 0.158 at +6° at 10 m/s), attributable to increased form drag and progressive flow separation at the trailing edge. At negative deflections, CD decreased progressively — approximately 7% reduction at -5° deflection at 20 m/s — as the upward trailing edge geometry reduced surface curvature and promoted smoother flow attachment.

6.3 Lift-to-Drag Ratio

The lift-to-drag ratio CL/CD peaked at 2.4 at +6° morphing deflection at 10 m/s — more than double the neutral baseline value of 1.14. This confirms that lift increases at a faster rate than drag across the positive deflection range, producing a net improvement in aerodynamic efficiency. Peak CL/CD values at 15 and 20 m/s were 2.09 and 2.01 respectively.

6.4 Comparison with NACA 0012 Baseline

The fixed NACA 0012 baseline, being symmetrical, produces zero lift at zero angle of attack. The morphing wing generates positive lift at zero incidence through camber modification, providing direct aerodynamic benefit at take-off and low-speed conditions. At negative deflections, the drag reduction advantage over the neutral baseline supports cruise efficiency optimisation.

7. Intellectual Property

UK Patent Application GB2610796.1

Title: 'Adaptive Morphing Wing System for Unmanned Aerial Vehicles'

Filed: 8 May 2026 | UK Intellectual Property Office, Newport

Claims: 10 claims covering structural configuration, hybrid material architecture, and actuation methodology

Inventor and Applicant: Rohankumar Rajeshbhai Patel (sole)

Commercial Development: AeroFlex Technologies Ltd, London, United Kingdom

8. Commercial Development — AeroFlex Technologies Ltd

AeroFlex Technologies Ltd is a UK company founded to commercialise the adaptive morphing wing system and related adaptive aerodynamic technologies for UAV applications. The company is registered with the University of Hertfordshire Enterprise Hub, connecting the research to structured UK innovation and business development support.

Commercial development strategy:

- Core IP asset: UK patent application GB2610796.1 covering the morphing wing architecture
- Target market: small UAV manufacturers in commercial, defence, and scientific sectors; next-generation air mobility platforms
- Funding pathway: Innovate UK Smart Grants and Future Flight Challenge programme applications planned
- Industry collaboration: strategic partnerships with UK aerospace companies and UAV manufacturers under development
- Research foundation: ongoing collaboration with University of Hertfordshire; peer-reviewed publication in preparation

9. Future Research Directions

- Submission and publication of peer-reviewed journal paper in MDPI Aerospace
- Multi-objective aerodynamic optimisation of the morphing geometry — gradient-based and machine learning methods
- Quantitative characterisation of the SMA micro-actuation contribution to aerodynamic performance (currently untested in isolation)
- Fatigue and durability assessment of TPU morphing skin under representative operational loading cycles
- Higher-fidelity CFD analysis using ANSYS Fluent with transient solver and full fluid-structure interaction modelling
- Multi-material FDM fabrication enabling single-step production of combined ABS-TPU hybrid wing structures
- Free-flight integration and aerodynamic validation of the morphing system in a flight-worthy small UAV platform
- Machine learning-based real-time adaptive shape control algorithms for in-flight optimisation

10. Acknowledgements

The author gratefully acknowledges the supervisory and ongoing mentorship contribution of Ben Stacey (Department of Engineering, University of Hertfordshire), who supervised the foundational BEng research project and continues as research mentor for the independent post-graduation development programme.

The author also acknowledges the technical support of Abhinav Balaji and James (University of Hertfordshire technical staff) for wind tunnel equipment setup and testing guidance, and Eduardo Gonzalez and Harley Collard (UH Fab-Lab) for 3D printing expertise and prototype fabrication support. The University of Hertfordshire is acknowledged for provision of laboratory, wind tunnel, and manufacturing facilities supporting the ongoing research.

References

- [1] Barbarino, S. et al. A review of morphing aircraft. *J. Intell. Mater. Syst. Struct.* 2011, 22, 823–877.
 - [2] Gandhi, F.; Anusonti-Inthra, P. Design of a morphing wingtip. *J. Aircr.* 2018, 55, 1056–1077.
 - [3] Sofla, A.Y.N. et al. Shape morphing of aircraft wing: Status and challenges. *Mater. Des.* 2010, 31, 1284–1292.
 - [4] Blakey-Milner, B. et al. Metal additive manufacturing in aerospace: A review. *Mater. Des.* 2021, 209, 110008.
 - [5] Jani, J.M. et al. A review of shape memory alloy research, applications and opportunities. *Mater. Des.* 2014, 56, 1078–1113.
 - [6] Ladson, C.L. et al. Computer Program to Obtain Ordinates for NACA Airfoils. NASA TM-4741, 1996.
 - [7] Gibson, I.; Rosen, D.; Stucker, B. *Additive Manufacturing Technologies*, 2nd ed. Springer, 2015.
 - [8] Lagoudas, D.C. (Ed.) *Shape Memory Alloys: Modeling and Engineering Applications*. Springer, 2008.
 - [9] Menter, F.R. Two-equation eddy-viscosity turbulence models for engineering applications. *AIAA J.* 1994, 32, 1598–1605.
 - [10] BASF SE. *Thermoplastic Polyurethane Properties — TPU Material Data Sheet, v5.2*. BASF, 2021.
-